

Stability of Ternary La^{III}, Ce^{III}, Pr^{III}, Nd^{III}, Sm^{III} and Y^{III} EGTA–Pyrocatechols

VISHNU KOLHE and K. DWIVEDI*

School of Studies in Chemistry, Jiwaji University, Gwalior-474 011

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In view of the biological importance of ethylene-glycolbis(2-aminoethylether)-*N, N, N', N'*-tetraacetic acid (EGTA), pyrocatechol and substituted pyrocatechols, a systematic investigation on ternary complexes of trivalent La, Ce, Pr, Nd, Sm and Y involving these ligands have been undertaken and the results are presented.

Results and Discussion

The proton-dissociation constants of the ligands and stability constants of binary and ternary complexes have been calculated by algebraic method¹ and are presented in Table 1. In the ternary systems, it is observed that the displacement of the experimental curve with the composite curve in the range $2 \leq a \leq 4$, $\text{pH} \approx 8.0$ indicates the liberation of extra protons due to the interaction of pyrocatechol (PYC), 4-methylpyrocatechol (MPYC), 4-nitropyrocatechol (NPYC) with [M(III)–EGTA] complex species. This can be illustrated by the equilibria,

Negative values² of $\Delta \log k$ (-4.0 ± 0.2) and percent relative stabilisation³ [(%) R. S.] (-41 ± 2) indicate that the secondary ligand (L) binds better to aquometal ion than the [M–EGTA][–] complex. It can be explained on the basis of the electrostatic repulsion between [M–EGTA][–] and incoming negatively charge secondary ligands, coupled with the availability of

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND AND M(III)–LIGAND BINARY AND TERNARY CONSTANTS WITH EGTA AND PYC, MPYC AND NPYC

Constant	M(III)	H ₂ A ^{2–} H ₂ EGTA ^{2–}	H ₂ L		
			PYC	MPYC	NPYC
Temp. = 25°, $\mu = 0$					
pK ₁	–	9.18	9.98	10.02	9.74
pK ₂	–	10.75	12.12	12.75	11.98
log K _{MA} ^M	La	15.55	9.37	9.49	9.22
	Ce	15.92	9.48	9.61	9.34
log K _{ML} ^M	Pr	16.02	9.56	9.74	9.40
	Nd	16.24	9.68	9.81	9.51
	Sm	16.75	9.80	9.88	9.63
	Y	17.10	9.88	9.95	9.75
	log K _{MAL} ^M	La	–	5.36	5.47
Ce		–	5.48	5.61	5.35
Pr		–	5.59	5.68	5.44
Nd		–	5.67	5.76	5.56
Sm		–	5.76	5.87	5.70
Y		–	5.87	6.05	5.81

lesser number of coordinating sites for coordination on [M–EGTA][–] binary complex compared to aquated metal ions. The formation of ternary complexes can also be evidenced by the study of the distribution of various complex species present in solution as a percentage of metal ion concentration and their variation with pH. Representative species distribution curves for the La(III)–EGTA–PYC system is shown in Fig. 1.

Stability order of binary and ternary complexes are found to be in accordance with the increasing ionic potential of metal ions, viz. La^{III} < Ce^{III} < Pr^{III} < Nd^{III} < Sm^{III} < Y^{III}, and the stability order with respect to secondary ligand follows the basicity order of the ligands, i.e. MPYC > PYC > NPYC.

Fig. 1. Species distribution of M(III)-EGTA-L' system.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of analytical grade and the solutions were prepared in double-distilled water. pH-metric titration of the following thermostated mixtures using an Elico LI-120 pH meter were carried out

at $25 \pm 1^\circ$ and three different ionic strengths i.e. $0.05M$, $0.10M$ and $0.15M$ (NaNO_3): (i) HNO_3 ($2.0 \times 10^{-3}M$), (ii) HNO_3 ($2.0 \times 10^{-3}M$) + ligand H_2A^{2-} ($1.0 \times 10^{-3}M$), (iii) HNO_3 ($2.0 \times 10^{-3}M$) + ligand H_2A^{2-} ($1.0 \times 10^{-3}M$) + metal ion ($1.0 \times 10^{-3}M$), (iv) HNO_3 ($2.0 \times 10^{-3}M$) + ligand L ($1.0 \times 10^{-3}M$), (v) HNO_3 ($2.0 \times 10^{-3}M$) + ligand L ($1.0 \times 10^{-3}M$), (vi) HNO_3 ($2.0 \times 10^{-3}M$) + ligand H_2A^{2-} ($1.0 \times 10^{-3}M$) + ligand L ($1.0 \times 10^{-3}M$) + metal ion ($1.0 \times 10^{-3}M$); where H_2A^{2-} = disodium salt of EGTA, L = PYC, MPYC and NPYC and metal(III) ion = La, Ce, Pr, Nd, Sm and Y.

References

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